

2019 UTC-UTI Workshop

Colorado School of Mines

October 18, 2019

USING DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS TO PREDICT SENSOR RESPONSE AND GEOLOGY AHEAD OF A TBM

Kabir Nagrecha
Luis Fisher Jr.
Mehran Mazari
Tona Rodriguez-Nikl
Mohammad Pourhomayoun

Computer Science
California State University Los Angeles

UNIVERSITY TRANSPORTATION CENTER
FOR UNDERGROUND TRANSPORTATION INFRASTRUCTURE

CAL STATE LA
CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES

Outline

- Project Introductions
- Context
- Objectives
- Project TBM State Prediction
 - Methodology
 - Results
- Project Geological Prediction
 - Methodology
 - Results
- Acknowledgements

Project Introductions

- Two projects on applications of deep learning to tunneling systems
- Works to address some of the primary issues in tunneling
- Potential improvements in performance, safety, and reduction in preparation times
- Projects addresses different critical areas – state prediction and soil prediction
- Using advanced deep learning techniques, we harness the massive data output of TBMs
- Continuously generate evolving predicted image of TBM state over time
- Understand and predict geological composition of surrounding soil with accuracy previously out of reach

Harnessing a Data-Rich Environment

Hallandsåstunneln TBM model

- TBMs generate massive amounts of information
- We can utilize this data to improve performance by gaining knowledge about the worksite and operation parameters
- Current statistical techniques are not sufficient to harness such massive amounts of data to great effect
- But using modern deep learning techniques

Dataset Collection

- Deep learning requires large datasets like those generated by TBMs
- For these projects we reached out to two tunneling projects who provided us with very large datasets representing months of tunneling

- Seattle Northgate Link Project

- LA Metro Gold Line Extension

Research Objectives

- Demonstrate deep learning's application to tunneling systems and underground transportation
- Apply machine learning to predict mechanical state of TBMs and geological composition of soil with accuracy comparable to traditional techniques
- Improve the safety and performance of TBM projects by providing critical information on the worksite environment – both geological and mechanical
- Reduce preparation times by exploiting transferability in machine learning systems

Geological Prediction - Overview

- Current systems tunnel without any real information on their outside surroundings – they have no understanding of soil composition around them
- Past studies have used geological data from boreholes to interpolate between the boreholes to get an understanding of soil composition
- But accuracy goes down as distance increases
- To address this, deep learning can be used to predict geological composition based on mechanical sensor outputs

Geological Prediction - Methodology

- Initial dataset was massive in size – over 30GB
- Domain knowledge applied to get an understanding of existing soil composition and what areas to predict
 - Predicting what percentage of the soil is formed by 4 different types
 - Cohesive Clay and Silt (CCS)
 - Cohesionless Silt and Fine Sand (CSF)
 - Cohesionless Sand and Gravel (CSG)
 - Till-Like Deposits (TLD)
- Feature selection and compression used to reduce number of features

Geological Prediction - Methodology

- The newly compressed data is fed into a predictive model known as an RNN-LSTM, a form of neural network
- The RNN-LSTM's key feature is its ability to predict time-based relationships
- This is critical to continuous geology

Geological Prediction - Results

- Accurate and capable results show a strong predictive model

Mechanical Prediction - Overview

- Utilize time-based nature of RNN-LSTM to not only predict the present, but the future
- Predict the TBM's state at future positions
- Use past sensor outputs to predict future sensor outputs
- Exploit similarities in sensory structure across TBM systems to transfer learning across projects – thus eliminating a great deal of preparation time

Mechanical Prediction - Methodology

- Initial dataset was large – several gigabytes
- Compression is used to reduce dataset size to a more manageable scope
- Correlation heatmaps used to eliminate tautological bias and false data
- RNN-LSTM system uses only mechanical data from past to predict future mechanical data – no future data and no explicit geological information
- Transfer systems tested – two tunnel dataset
- 4 main sensor outputs predicted
 - Advance Speed, Articulation Force, Cutterhead Speed, Thrust Force

Mechanical Prediction - Results

- Training and testing one tunnel showed excellent accuracy

Mechanical Prediction - Results

Training on one tunnel, testing on the other

Training on one tunnel, retraining lightly on the other, testing on the rest

Acknowledgement(s)

- Support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) is gratefully acknowledged.
- Support from Jay Dee Constructors for providing the data used throughout this study.
- Support from LA Metro Rail for providing the data used throughout this study.